

Clinicopathological Study of Long-Term Female Tubal Sterilization Failures at a Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

Introduction: Female tubal sterilization is a widely accepted permanent method of contraception, particularly in developing countries. Despite its effectiveness, failures occur due to improper surgical techniques, spontaneous recanalization, or anatomical variations, leading to unintended pregnancies and increased risks of ectopic gestation and maternal morbidity. This study aims to identify the clinicopathological factors contributing to sterilization failures and assess pregnancy outcomes and demographic characteristics of affected women.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective study was conducted at the Government Medical College and Hospital, analyzing cases of sterilization failure over a ten-year period (April 2014 to March 2024). Excluding luteal phase pregnancies, data were collected from patient records, focusing on variables such as patient demographics, sterilization techniques, time to failure, pregnancy management strategies, and re-sterilization outcomes. Management was customized based on each case, with thorough counseling and follow-up provided to optimize patient outcomes and prevent future failures.

Results: Over the ten-year period, sterilization failures were most common in 2016–2017 and 2020–2021 (18 cases each) and least in 2021–2022 (4 cases). The highest incidence was in the 25-29 age group, with laparoscopic procedures being the most frequent (60 cases), followed by LSCS-based sterilizations (42 cases). Improper procedures accounted for 22 cases, primarily involving misplaced bands, while tuboperitoneal fistula was the leading cause of failure (45.6%). More than half of the failures (51.66%) occurred within five years, with 38.33% of pregnancies detected in the first trimester, 26.66% in the second, and 35% progressing beyond 20 weeks. Re-sterilization efforts were led by bilateral partial salpingectomy (71.88%), with ectopic pregnancies more prevalent following minilap procedures (79%) compared to laparoscopic methods (14%). Most failures (60%) originated from Primary Health Centers, highlighting the need for improved training and surgical precision.

Conclusion: Our findings emphasize the importance of skilled surgical techniques and timely follow-up to reduce sterilization failures, with a focus on strengthening protocols at Primary Health Centers to minimize risks and ensure optimal patient outcomes.

Keywords: Sterilization failure, Ectopic pregnancy, Recanalization, Laparoscopic sterilization, Minilaparotomy.

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Introduction

Female tubal sterilization is one of the most widely accepted permanent methods of contraception across the globe, particularly in developing countries where family planning initiatives emphasize population control. [1] Despite being a highly effective method with a low reported failure rate, sterilization failures continue to pose significant clinical, psychological, and social challenges for women. [2] These failures can occur due to various factors such as improper surgical techniques, incomplete occlusion of the fallopian

tubes, spontaneous recanalization, or anatomical variations. [3] Understanding the causes and consequences of sterilization failure is essential not only for improving surgical protocols but also for guiding counseling strategies to minimize emotional distress and unintended pregnancies. [4]

The consequences of sterilization failure can be serious, often resulting in unintended pregnancies that carry higher risks of ectopic gestation and maternal morbidity. [5] This is particularly

concerning since women who undergo sterilization often belong to vulnerable socioeconomic groups, for whom an unplanned pregnancy may impose significant financial and psychological burdens. Moreover, sterilization failures may undermine public trust in family planning programs, highlighting the need for meticulous surgical techniques and robust follow-up protocols. [6] Through the evaluation of cases involving long-term sterilization failures, this study aims to identify the clinicopathological factors associated with these failures, assess the patterns of ectopic pregnancies, and examine the demographic characteristics of affected women.

Materials and Methods

This study presents a retrospective analysis carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at the Government Medical College and Hospital. It focuses on all cases of tubal sterilization failures reported or referred to the institution over a ten-year span, from April 2014 to March 2024. Notably, pregnancies occurring in the luteal phase—those conceived immediately before sterilization—were excluded from the definition of failure in this analysis. The data were extracted from archived patient records within the hospital, ensuring anonymity throughout the study. As no personally identifiable information was disclosed, formal consent from participants was not required.

The study captured key variables, including the age and obstetric history of patients, the type and site of sterilization, and the time elapsed between the sterilization procedure and its failure. Additionally, it documented the gestational age at diagnosis and the couple's decision regarding whether to continue or terminate the pregnancy. A vital aspect of the analysis was to explore the couples' preferences for re-sterilization and their reproductive choices following the failure.

Pregnancy management strategies were tailored to the specific needs of each case, taking into account the patient's previous obstetric outcomes, the gestational period, and overall health. Couples were guided through their options for either continuing

or terminating the pregnancy, with an emphasis on ensuring maternal safety and well-being. Thorough counseling sessions were provided to support them in making informed decisions throughout the process.

Re-sterilization procedures involved a meticulous evaluation of the original sterilization method to determine the reason for failure. The analysis looked for issues such as technical errors, spontaneous tubal recanalization, or non-functional but structurally intact fallopian tube segments. Any additional findings that might have contributed to the failure were also recorded.

The selection of re-sterilization techniques was customized based on the surgical findings and the anatomical condition of the reproductive organs. The goal was to ensure the long-term success of the procedure, minimizing the likelihood of future failures. Postoperative care and follow-up were integral to the process, with a focus on monitoring recovery and verifying the effectiveness of the re-sterilization to prevent recurrence.

Results

In our study, sterilization failures varied significantly over the ten-year period. The highest number of failures (18 cases) occurred in two distinct years: 2016–2017 and 2020–2021. The lowest incidence was observed in 2021–2022, with only 4 cases. (Figure 1) In our study, the majority of cases (49) fell within the 25-29 age group, reflecting a high prevalence of sterilization procedures in this reproductive age range. Women aged over 30 years accounted for 35 cases, while the 20-24 age group had the fewest cases (16). The type of sterilization surgery performed varied across the cases studied. Laparoscopic procedures (Lap) were the most common, with 60 cases, highlighting the popularity of minimally invasive methods. Sterilization performed during cesarean sections (LSCS) accounted for 42 cases, reflecting the trend of combining sterilization with delivery. Mini-laparotomy (Mini Lap) was the least common, with only 3 cases. In terms of parity, 50% of the women were para 2.

Figure 1: Year-wise distribution of cases

In our study, 22 cases were identified with improper sterilization procedures. The most common issue was the placement of a band on the right mesosalpinx or round ligament, which occurred in 7 cases (31.82%). Incomplete tubal ligation on either the right or left side was observed in 5 cases each (22.73%). (Table 1)

Table 1: Improper Procedure Details

Improper Procedure	Number	Percentage (%)
Tubal ligation not performed on right side	5	22.73%
Tubal ligation not performed on left side	5	22.73%
Band placed at right mesosalpinx or round ligament	7	31.82%
Band placed at left mesosalpinx or round ligament	1	4.55%
Bands at mesosalpinx on both sides	2	9.09%
Left side band partially placed	1	4.55%
Right side band at mesosalpinx + no band on left side	1	4.55%
Total	22	100%

Re-sterilization procedures were necessary for patients to prevent future failures. The most common procedure performed was bilateral partial salpingectomy, accounting for 46 cases (71.88%). This was followed by bilateral salpingectomy (30 cases, 46.88%) and fimbriectomy (19 cases, 29.69%). (Table 2)

Table 2: Re-Sterilization Procedure Details

Re-Sterilization Procedures	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Bilateral partial salpingectomy	46	71.88%
Bilateral fimbriectomy	19	29.69%
Bilateral salpingectomy	30	46.88%
Right salpingo-oophorectomy	1	1.56%
Left tubo-ovarian mass excision	1	1.56%
Right tubo-ovarian mass excision	1	1.56%
Left salpingectomy	2	3.13%
Total	100	100%

Several incidental findings were noted during re-sterilization, highlighting potential anatomical abnormalities contributing to sterilization failures. Hydrosalpinx was found in 3 cases (23.08%), with 2 cases on the right side and 1 on the left. Tubo-ovarian masses were observed in 2 patients (15.38%), one on each side. Additionally,

bicornuate uterus, a congenital anomaly that can complicate pregnancies, was identified in 2 cases (15.38%). Omental adhesions were noted in 5 cases (38.46%), indicating possible previous surgical or inflammatory issues that could have influenced the outcome of sterilization.

Figure 2: Incidental Findings

The sterilization failure interval varied, with 19.16% of cases occurring within the first year, 51.66% between 1-5 years, 24.16% between 6-10 years, and 5% after more than 10 years (Figure 3). This data indicates that more than half of the failures occurred within the first five years post-sterilization, with only a small percentage

occurring after a decade. When analyzing the place of previous sterilization, 60% of the procedures were performed at Primary Health Centers (PHCs), followed by 18.33% at rural hospitals, 10% at tertiary centers, 6.66% at private hospitals, and 5% at camps.

Figure 3: Sterilization-failure interval

In terms of pregnancy outcomes, 38.33% of the failures were detected in the first trimester, of which 33.33% underwent first-trimester medical termination of pregnancy (MTP), and 5% required laparotomy due to ectopic pregnancies. For pregnancies between 12-20 weeks (26.66%), 22.5%

underwent second-trimester MTP, while 4.16% required hysterotomy for obstetric reasons. In cases where pregnancy extended beyond 20 weeks (35%), 20% delivered vaginally at term, 8.33% had preterm deliveries, and 6.66% required LSCS.

Figure 4: Final Management (%)

Regarding the causes of sterilization failure, recanalization was identified in 16.66% of cases, with 6.66% involving ectopic pregnancies. Improper procedures were responsible for 18.33% of failures, while tuboperitoneal fistula accounted for 36.66% of cases. In 21.66% of cases, the exact cause of failure could not be determined. When comparing types of sterilization, 78% of the improper procedures occurred in Lap TL, while 22% were associated with minilap procedures. In terms of recanalization, 52% of cases occurred with minilap, 44% with Lap TL, and 4% with LSCS. Similarly, ectopic pregnancies were more common following minilap (79%), followed by Lap TL (14%), and LSCS (7%). Tuboperitoneal fistula was the most common etiology, accounting for 45.6% of the cases. Improper procedures were responsible for 18.33% of failures, while recanalization occurred in 16.66% of cases. Additionally, 18% of cases could not be evaluated as patients were not available for follow-up. A small proportion (1.49%) involved failures due to rare causes or other unknown factors.

Discussion

The likelihood of sterilization failure appears notably higher among younger women. Research highlights that approximately 65% of failures occur in women under 30 years of age, consistent with findings by Ehman et al. [7] who documented similar challenges in this demographic, especially with early sterilization requests and subsequent regret risks. In contrast to earlier studies by Kulier et al. [8], which found no substantial difference between laparoscopic and minilaparotomy methods, our study revealed a higher failure rate with minilaparotomy (59%) than laparoscopic sterilization (38%). [9]

Interestingly, our findings align with Rathod and Samal [10], where spontaneous recanalization was identified in over 50% of sterilization failures, highlighting the persistent risk of tubal patency

restoration despite initial surgical success. Furthermore, our rare case of double failure following separate procedures echoes the experience reported by Sharma et al. [11], who encountered multiple ectopic pregnancies linked to failed ligations over a decade. To mitigate future failures, bilateral salpingectomy was performed, although, as noted in the literature by Brahmanandan et al. [12], even this technique is not entirely foolproof, with rare cases of post-salpingectomy pregnancies documented in clinical settings.

In our study, 65.48% of failures occurred within 1 to 10 years, a finding that aligns with studies by Sharma et al. [11] and Rani et al. [13], which similarly reported the majority of failures during this period due to recanalization or fistula formation. While the longest failure interval documented in literature extends to 23 years, our study recorded a maximum interval of 11 years. [13] Early failures, occurring within one year, were mostly attributed to improper procedures, reflecting the conclusions of Rathod and Samal [10], who identified technical errors and non-occlusion as key contributors. In contrast, late failures were often linked to spontaneous tubal reapproximation or tuboperitoneal fistula formation, consistent with observations by Vanitha et al. [9]

Improper laparoscopic sterilization accounted for 78% of early failures, echoing the findings of Vanitha et al. [9] and Brahmanandan et al. [12], who highlighted the risks associated with inadequate occlusive methods and spontaneous luminal regeneration in resectional techniques. Although tubal patency is occasionally observed after successful sterilization, patency alone does not imply failure, as pregnancy rates remain low despite documented patency rates of up to 16% at five years. [13] Moreover, 60% of our failures were associated with procedures performed at Primary Health Centers (PHCs), reinforcing the conclusions of Sharma et al. [11] and Rani et al. [13], who

attributed high failure rates to insufficient surgical expertise in such settings. Premalatha and Tripathi also emphasized that adherence to proper sterilization protocols was noted in fewer than 17% of cases, underscoring the need for improved training and guidelines to prevent such failures. [14]

Our study identified pre-existing gynecological pathologies and müllerian anomalies as contributing factors to sterilization failure, consistent with reports by Sharma et al. [11] and Rani et al. [13] Such conditions were also noted in several of our cases. Ectopic pregnancies occurred in 4.55% of failures within the first year and 7.5% between 1-5 years, aligning with findings from Shah et al. [15] and Bhatnagar [16], who documented similar trends in early ectopic gestations following sterilization. Beyond five years, ectopic pregnancies accounted for 37.5% of failures, supporting the observations of Varma and Gupta [17] that spontaneous tubal regeneration over time contributes to late ectopic presentations. Notably, 79% of the ectopic pregnancies in our study followed minilap procedures, suggesting a higher risk associated with this technique.

In managing pregnancies resulting from sterilization failure, strategies vary depending on gestational age, patient health, and institutional protocols. Our study found that 38.33% of failed pregnancies were identified during the first trimester, with 33.33% undergoing medical termination of pregnancy (MTP) and 5% requiring laparotomy for ectopic pregnancies. These findings align with those of Brahmanandan et al.¹², who observed that early detection often leads to MTP, especially when failure results in ectopic gestation, highlighting the importance of timely intervention to reduce morbidity. Similarly, Rathod and Samal [10] emphasized the role of immediate surgical management for ectopic pregnancies, with laparotomy being a common approach when rupture occurs due to delayed detection.

Pregnancies between 12-20 weeks accounted for 26.66% of failures in our study, with 22.5% undergoing second-trimester MTP and 4.16% requiring hysterotomy due to complications. These outcomes are consistent with Sharma et al. [11], who reported similar patterns, noting that management at this stage often involves complex decisions regarding fetal viability and maternal health. In comparison, Vanitha et al.⁹ observed that second-trimester failures frequently required surgical interventions, such as hysterotomy or LSCS, particularly when pregnancy termination was delayed or associated with obstetric complications.

For pregnancies that extended beyond 20 weeks, 20% in our study delivered vaginally at term,

8.33% had preterm deliveries, and 6.66% required LSCS. This pattern aligns with findings by Rani et al. [13], who noted that pregnancies detected late or continued to term often led to deliveries through cesarean section due to higher risks of complications. Across studies, ensuring timely follow-up, comprehensive counseling, and personalized care emerge as critical factors in optimizing pregnancy outcomes following sterilization failure. [3,12]

Our study has several limitations. First, being a retrospective analysis, it relies heavily on the accuracy and completeness of medical records, which may have introduced information bias. Additionally, follow-up data were incomplete in 18% of cases, limiting our ability to fully assess long-term outcomes and causes of failure. The study was also confined to a single institution, which may affect the generalizability of the findings to other settings with different surgical practices or patient demographics. Another limitation is the inability to account for all potential confounding factors, such as surgeon expertise and variations in sterilization techniques across facilities. Lastly, the reliance on patient-reported outcomes for some follow-ups may have led to underreporting of complications or recanalization cases.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study highlights the complexities of managing pregnancies resulting from sterilization failures, emphasizing the importance of early detection and tailored interventions. A significant proportion of early failures were managed through MTP, while second-trimester cases often required more invasive procedures like hysterotomy or LSCS due to complications. Late-detected pregnancies, particularly beyond 20 weeks, were predominantly managed through vaginal delivery or cesarean section, reflecting the diverse clinical scenarios encountered. The high prevalence of ectopic pregnancies, especially following minilap procedures, underscores the need for meticulous surgical techniques and strict adherence to sterilization protocols.

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